

Polyelectrolyte-dye interactions : Study of interaction between Sodium Carboxymethylcellulose and Acridine Orange

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Abstract : The interaction between Sodium Carboxymethylcellulose (NaCMC) and a fluorescent cationic dye, Acridine Orange (AO) has been investigated by spectrophotometric and spectrofluorometric methods. The polymer induces metachromasy in the dye as evidenced from the considerable blue shift in the absorption maximum of the dye. The interaction constant and thermodynamic parameters of polymer-dye interactions have been determined by the absorbance and fluorescence measurements. The effect of additives such as alcohols and urea on the reversal of metachromasy has been studied. The data has been used to determine the stability of the metachromatic complex and the nature of binding.

Keywords : Sodium Carboxymethylcellulose, Acridine Orange, metachromasy, polyelectrolyte, stoichiometry, thermodynamic parameters.

Introduction

Metachromasy induced in various cationic dyes by polysaccharides containing carboxylate and sulphate groups and different synthetic polyanions is well studied¹⁻⁴. The interaction of various bacterial polysaccharides like Klebsiella K-17, K-10, K-14, K-16 and K-20 with cationic dyes like Acridine Orange, pinacyanol chloride, and phenosafranin etc. has been studied by Chakraborty *et al.*⁵⁻⁹ and the thermodynamic parameters of interaction have been reported. The studies on synthetic polyanions inducing metachromasy in different cationic dyes are also reported in literature¹⁰⁻¹². Measurements of fluorescence intensity of the dye molecules in the presence of polymers has also been used as a tool to understand the polymer-dye interactions¹³⁻¹⁶. The cationic, fluorescent dye, AO, has been found to be a good dye system for the study of polymer-dye interactions¹⁷⁻²¹.

The objective of the present study is to understand the formation of complex between NaCMC, an anionic polyelectrolyte and AO by absorption and fluorescence measurements of the dye in the presence of the polymer and to evaluate the thermodynamic parameters of interaction. The extent of metachromasy induced in the

dye molecule by the polymer and the reversal of metachromasy by the addition of ionic salts, alcohols and urea has been studied in order to understand the interaction between polymer and dye molecules.

Experimental

Acridine Orange (AO) was obtained from S.D. Fine Chemicals, Mumbai and used as received. Sodium Carboxymethylcellulose (NaCMC) (B.D.H.) was used as received. Standard methods were used to determine the DS²² and (M_v)²³ of the NaCMC sample. Methanol and 2-propanol (Merck) were distilled before use. Urea (Merck) was used as received. Absorption spectra were recorded using a Shimadzu UV-2550 spectrophotometer. The concentration of the stock aqueous solutions of the dye and the polymer were $6 \times 10^{-5} M$ and $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ respectively.

Determination of stoichiometry of polymer-dye complex : Increasing amounts of polymer solution (0.0–9 ml, $1 \times 10^{-3} M$) were added to fixed volume of dye solution (0.6 ml, $1 \times 10^{-3} M$) in different sets of experiments and the total volume was made up to 10 ml by adding distilled water in each case. The absorbance were measured at 492 and 464 nm.

The effect of alcohols namely, methanol, 2-propanol and urea on the spectra of the pure dye was studied by measuring absorbance of the pure dye solution at 492 nm in the presence of alcohols and urea. 10 ml solutions were made with 0.6 ml of 1×10^{-3} M dye and remaining alcohol (10–80%) or aqueous urea (1–8 M) and the absorbances were recorded at 492 nm.

For measurements of the reversal of metachromasy, solutions containing polymer and dye in the ratio 5 : 1 were made containing different amount of alcohol. The total volume was maintained at 10 ml in each case. The absorbances were measured at 464 and 492 nm. Similarly, polymer-dye solutions containing different amounts of urea (1–8 M) were made and the absorbances were measured at 492 and 464 nm.

Fluorescent studies : Fluorescence of the dye solutions as well as that dye-polymer mixture was measured using AB2 Luminescence Spectrometer Ver. 5.80. Spectrofluorometric titrations were carried out by measuring fluorescence intensity of the AO solutions, at the emission peak, 529 nm upon addition of increasing amounts of polymer sample under separate experiments. The concentration of the aqueous solution of the dye was 6×10^{-5} M. The concentration of the polymer solution varied from 10^{-3} – 10^{-4} M. Increasing amounts of polymer solution (0.0–9 ml, 1×10^{-3} M) were added to fixed volume of dye solution (0.6 ml, 1×10^{-3} M) in different sets of experiments and the total volume was made up to 10 ml by adding distilled water in each case.

The thermodynamic parameters were determined by measuring the absorbances of the pure dye solution at both 464 and at 492 nm in the temperature range (35–55 °C). The above experiments were repeated in presence of the polymer at various polymer-dye ratios (2, 5, 10, 20).

Results and discussion

The absorption spectra of Acridine Orange (1) at various concentrations are shown in Fig. 1. They show a single band with absorption maximum at 492 nm indicating the presence of a monomeric dye species in the range of concentration studied. The spectral changes on addition of increasing amount of NaCMC are shown in Fig. 2.

The intensity at 492 nm decreases progressively upon addition of increasing amounts of polymer solution and the absorption maximum shifts to 464 nm. The blue shifted band is attributed to the stacking of the dye molecules on the polymer backbone, which reflects high degree of co-operativity in binding²⁰.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of dye, AO.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectrum of polymer-dye system at various P/D ratios ([dye] = 6×10^{-3} M).

Determination of stoichiometry : To determine the stoichiometry of the polymer-dye complex, a plot of A_{464}/A_{492} versus the polymer/dye ratio was made and is shown in Fig. 3. The stoichiometry of AO-NaCMC complex was found to be 2 : 1 which indicates that the binding is at alternate anionic sites. This indicates that there is lesser overcrowding the more aggregation of the bound dyes

on the polymer chain. Similar results were reported in case of binding of pincyanol chloride on poly(methacrylic acid) and poly(styrene sulfonate) systems²¹.

Fig. 3. Stoichiometry of AO-NaCMC complex.

Reversal of metachromasy using alcohols and urea :

The metachromatic effect is presumably due to the association of the dye molecules on binding with the polyanion which may involve both electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions. The destruction of metachromatic effect may occur on addition of low molecular weight electrolytes, alcohols or urea. The destruction of metachromasy by alcohol and urea is attributed to the involvement of hydrophobic bond in the induction of metachromasy. The fact that urea weakens hydrophobic bonding has already been established²⁷⁻³⁰. The efficiency of alcohols in disrupting metachromasy was found to be in the order : methanol < ethanol < 2-propanol, indicating that reversal becomes quicker with increasing hydrophobic character of the alcohols. The above facts are further established in the present system. As shown in Fig. 4, on addition of increasing amount of alcohol to the polymer/dye system at P/D = 5.0, the original monomeric band of dye species is gradually restored. The efficiency of two alcohols, namely methanol and propanol, on destruction of metachromasy was studied. As shown in Fig. 5, 40% methanol and 30% 2-propanol were required to reverse metachromasy in the present system.

Fig. 4. Effect of methanol on the reversal of metachromasy (dye conc : 6×10^{-5} M and P/D = 5.0).

Fig. 5. Reversal of metachromasy on addition of alcohols (dye conc : 6×10^{-5} M and P/D = 5.0).

Fig. 6. Reversal of metachromasy on addition of urea (dye conc : 6×10^{-5} M and P/D = 5.0).

However the concentration of urea to reverse metachromasy is found to be as high as 5 M (Fig. 6). Similar reports are reported in literature for reversal of metachromasy in anionic polyelectrolyte/cationic systems by addition of alcohols or urea³¹⁻³³.

Determination of interaction parameters : The interaction constant K_c for the complex of AO and NaCMC was determined by absorbance measurements at the metachromatic band at four different temperatures taking different sets of solutions containing varying amounts of polymer (C_s) in a fixed volume of the dye solution.

Fig. 7. Plots of $C_D \cdot C_s / (A - A_0)$ against C_s for AO-NaCMC system at different temperatures.

The absorbance (AO) of the pure dye (C_D) solution was also measured at the metachromatic band. Absorbance results were treated using Rose-Drago equation³⁴ given below.

$$C_D \cdot C_s / (A - A_0) = 1/K_c L (\epsilon_{ds} - \epsilon_d) + C_s / L (\epsilon_{ds} - \epsilon_d)$$

The value of K_c was obtained from the slope and intercept of the plot of $C_D \cdot C_s / (A - A_0)$ against C_s shown in Fig. 7. In each case the thermodynamic parameters of interaction, namely, ΔG , ΔH and ΔS were also calculated (Figs. 8 and 9). The results are tabulated in Table 1.

The values of interaction constant of AO-NaCMC decreases with rise in temperature suggesting exothermic nature of interaction and a negative ΔH also supported this fact. The value of ΔG is low and is of the order of reversible biological processes³⁵. The negative value of entropy indicated a more ordered state of the ions due to its aggregation. Thus all these thermodynamic parameters

suggested the interaction between the anionic sites on the polymer and the dye cations resulting in aggregation and induction of metachromasy.

Table 1. Thermodynamic parameters for interaction of AO-NaCMC

Temp. (K)	K_c ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) ^a	ΔG (kcal mol^{-1}) ^b	ΔH (kcal mol^{-1}) ^c	ΔS ($\text{cal mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) ^d
309	6366	-5.377		
315	3700	-5.142		
321	3214	-5.150	-11.0	-8.57
327	2222	-5.006		

^aCalculated from Fig. 2 according to Rose-Drago equation.

^bCalculated from the thermodynamic equation $\Delta G = -RT \ln K_c$.

^cCalculated graphically by plotting $\ln K_c$ against $1/T$ according to Vant Hoff equation, $\ln K_c = \Delta H/RT + C$.

^dCalculated from the thermodynamic expression $\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S$.

Fig. 8. Variation of ΔG with temperature.

Fig. 9. Vant' Hoff plot for AO-NaCMC system.

Fluorescence measurements : Fluorescent studies were performed with AO-NaCMC system and it was found that the intensity of the emission band of AO at 529 nm decreased after the addition of increasing amounts of polymer solution as shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10. Emission spectra of AO at various P/D ratios (dye conc : $6 \times 10^{-5} M$).

To study the interaction between the polymer and dye, the fluorescence data were fitted to Stern-Volmer equation,

$$F_0/F = 1 + K_{SV}[Q]$$

where F_0 is the fluorescence intensity of the dye solution and F is that of the dye-polymer mixture, $[Q]$ the molar concentration of the polymer and K_{SV} is the Stern-Volmer constant³⁶. The Stern-Volmer plots obtained for the present system is shown in Fig. 11. The linearity of the plot indicates static type of quenching in the present polymer-

Fig. 11. Stern-Volmer plot for AO-NaCMC system (dye conc $6 \times 10^{-5} M$).

dye system. The constant K_{SV} obtained from the slope of the plot of F_0/F is found to be $1.49 \times 10^4 dm^3 mol^{-1}$ indicating weak binding.

Conclusions :

The polymer NaCMC is observed to be effective in inducing metachromasy in the dye AO. The absorption band at 492 nm arises from the monomeric form of the dye while the absorption band due to the aggregated form of the dye appears at 464 nm. The dye is found to bind to alternate sites on the polymer giving the stoichiometry of polymer-dye complex to be 2.0. The study of the effect of alcohols and urea on the reversal of metachromasy indicates weak binding between AO-NaCMC, which is evident from the thermodynamic data and fluorescence study. Thus the binding between AO-NaCMC is governed by weak electrostatic interaction between the dye molecules and anionic sites on the polymer chain and the existence of hydrophobic interaction between bound dye molecules brings about aggregation of dye species. Thus the spectral studies prove the chromotropic character of NaCMC and the cooperative nature of dye-polymer interactions in NaCMC and AO system.

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